

THE NEED, PRINCIPLE AND SUPPORTS OF THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY

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Abstract: The process of globalization requires a qualitative renewal of the technological base of industrialized countries, a transition to a modernized economy to a new technological structure that ensures the improvement of the quality of life and living environment, while increasing the level of production efficiency and competitiveness. This article analyzes the problem of limited resources, the need to transition to a green economy, its principles and levers in the territory of Uzbekistan.

Key words: Green Economy, Brown economy, environmental problems, natural resources, economic sectors, agriculture and infrastructure sectors.

In fact, a lot of work is being done to green the economy in our country, including state laws on green economy. For example, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to increase the effectiveness of reforms aimed at the transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a Green Economy by 2030" dated December 2, 2022 PQ-436 in order to ensure its implementation, the Cabinet of Ministers decides:

1. Expenditure plan for the transition to a Green economy and ensuring Green growth in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, approved by the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-436 of December 2, 2022 In paragraph 58:

- assigning the task of coordination of "green" economy issues to one of the current deputy heads of state administration bodies and business associations;

- let it be accepted for information that it is envisaged to determine the units responsible for dealing with "green" economy issues in state administration bodies and economic associations to one hundred percent. The production and use of ecologically improved motor fuel and automobiles will be expanded, and electric transport will be developed.

2. Executive authorities of the Republic and heads of economic associations with a state share of 50 percent or more in the charter fund (charter capital) within two weeks, based on relevant decisions and/or orders:

- that one of the current deputy leaders is entrusted with the task of coordinating Green economy issues;

- establishment of a department responsible for dealing with Green economy issues within existing state units,

- as well as ensure the approval of its charter, which stipulates its goals and tasks.

The appearance of the world changed significantly in the 20th century. In 1900, the world population was 1.6 billion. person, in 2000 this indicator was 6 billion. has exceeded 7.8 billion people by 2021 is organizing a person. The average life expectancy of the population has almost doubled worldwide, and the poverty rate has decreased by more than 3 times. Economic development and the rapid growth of the population's standard of living under the influence of scientific and technical achievements have caused the world's population to increase rapidly. Scientific and technical achievements have provided high rates of economic development compared to the growth rates of the world population. For example, during the 20th century, the world's population increased by 3.6 times, while the world gross domestic product increased by more than 18 times. [1]

According to the analysis, the increase in the world population and economic growth have led to a regular increase in the burden on the environment. Due to the increase in population and economic activity in the last hundred years, the level of oxidation of the world's oceans has increased by almost 1.2 times (in 2000 compared to 1900), the rate of tropical forest loss has increased by 6 times, and carbon dioxide emissions have increased by 1.5 times increased. Such climate changes, which are occurring as a result of the increase in the economic activity of the world's population, may have serious consequences in the medium term.

The goals and strategic objectives of transition to the Green economy require basing on strategic principles. The principles of the transition to a Green economy determine how this economy should be. The principles of the Green economy are comprehensive compared to the principles of the Brown economy, and in 1972, at the international conference on socio-economic development and environmental problems in Stockholm, 26 principles aimed at the preservation and development of the environment were developed.

The need for sustainable development and introduction of Green elements in Uzbekistan consists of the following:

-Transition from a raw material-based, export-based economy to a sustainable and green economy.

- Introduction of new technologies and innovations to reduce environmental impact.

-Improving management and conservation of natural resources.

- Development of ecologically clean energy types.

- Increasing environmental education and culture of the population.

-Creating conditions for attracting investments in environmentally friendly projects.

Levers for investing in green projects: - green bonds; - loans; - direct investments;

- grants and donations.

Green technologies are aimed at achieving the following goals:

1. Reducing pollution and increasing resource efficiency in the design of construction, production, agriculture and infrastructure sectors, as well as urbanization processes.

2. Mitigate adverse climate change, hydrocarbon sequestration and accumulation by transitioning to greener, cleaner energy and low-carbon end-use processes.

3. Reduce vulnerability and adapt to climate change by developing early warning systems and temperature-resistant technologies; improving the management of biodiversity and forest resources.

4. Improving well-being through more efficient and sustainable use of biodiversity resources, including natural cosmetics and pharmaceuticals.

In conclusion, by introducing green technologies, we can improve people's well-being and achieve sustainable environmental resources. This will benefit our country both economically and ecologically. That is, the more moderate people treat nature, the higher the rate of rational use of its resources, the more likely we are to achieve a sustainable Green Economy.

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